

UDC 004

COMBINING DIGITAL STORIES WITH THE INTERNET

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КОМБИНИРОВАНИЕ ЦИФРОВЫХ ИСТОРИЙ С ИНТЕРНЕТОМ

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Abstract. The Internet has the potential to enhance writing and literacy skills while offering a uniquely stylized form of expression. They are an excellent way to use educational technology and storytelling inside the classroom and beyond school walls. Producing digital stories give opportunities to self-expression encouraging creativity. They are both individualistic and collaborative because reading and writing can be used in a variety of academic contexts.

Аннотация. Интернет имеет потенциал для повышения навыков письма и грамотности, одновременно предлагая уникальную стилизованную форму выражения. Это отличный способ использовать образовательные технологии и изложение историй в классе и за пределами школьных стен.

Создание цифровых историй дает возможность для самовыражения, поощряя творчество. Они являются индивидуалистическими и совместными, поскольку чтение и письмо можно использовать в различных академических контекстах.

Keywords: digital story, literacy, searching information, websites, servers, creativity, Internet.

Ключевые слова: цифровая история, грамотность, поиск информации, веб-сайты, серверы, творчество, интернет.

Internet and digital stories in learning the language, at first sight, seems like not so related to each other. But when you work on them more, you will definitely find them connected with each other. Let's take the internet first. The Internet is a powerful tool to learn a language. You can use many websites which offer learning languages in order to improve your vocabulary, grammar, listening, reading, writing and speaking skills on these sites. In other words, the internet is like a universal tool to learn a language (1).

And now let's look at digital stories in learning languages. When you listen to digital stories you usually listen, read the script and watch the pictures or videos. And this can help you to improve your reading and listening skills. But if you produce a digital story you can improve more skills. When you write the script for your story you improve your writing skills. After finishing writing your script you have to read it in order to check for mistakes. And it helps you to improve your reading skills. When you finish checking the script you read it and record your own voice [1].

Speaking to the microphone and recording your voice is one of the best exercises to speak fluently. After finishing recording you listen to the audio and check your pronunciation for mistakes, that is to say, you will improve your listening skill.

At this point as you see the internet and digital stories have a lot of things in common. They both can help you learn a language comprehensively. What if we combine these two powerful tools together? This means saving more time, energy and making learning fun and easier. So let's see what if we combine them together [2].

When you make a digital story you usually have a particular topic and ideas on the topic. Starting your work you may need some information about your topic. And the quickest way to find any information is searching on the internet. Using the internet as a tool to make a digital story can be an option for you but without that option, you may waste more time and energy. And using the internet can make your work more beautiful and more professional.

All the steps for creating a digital story can be taken with the help of the internet. Downloading computer programs to edit your story, searching information for your story, picking up images and music can be easily done if you have an access to the internet. At the end when you finish making your digital story you can publish it on different websites and share it with other people.

To share your product you can use different websites or servers. For example, youtube for sharing videos or google drive to share nearly any kind of information or opening a facebook page and invite the people to the group and share your product with them. Or you can use all these together connecting them with each other. By doing this you make a combination of digital stories and the internet.

Let's see how to make this combination through the following quick steps:

1. You get a topic and start learning it and find all the information about the topic, including all the images and music.
2. Create a digital story using special programs on the computer.
3. After finishing your digital story open facebook or google account.
4. Upload your digital story to these websites and invite people to share your digital story and have a discussion on your topic, get comments and more ideas from them.
5. To connect these accounts leave a link of your facebook page on your google account or vice versa. It will help you to call more people to your accounts [3].

The more people you share your story with, the more feedbacks, ideas, and advice you will get from people. The more you get, the more you will learn. To get more you should give more. If a digital story is your product the internet can be a prize or a reward you will get from it. If you make more digital stories you will learn the language faster and if you share it with other people you will double the speed and you will learn more.

Internet and digital stories together can promote critical and analytical thinking; be a powerful promoter of creative, intuitive, and associational thinking; promote analogical thinking; be a powerful medium for increasing access and exposure to quality information and combine the best of solitary reflection and social interaction.

To conclude, modern teachers use different tools during the lesson and let their students do the same in order to see their creativity and what they can do or produce. So what kind of technologies do the teachers and students can use in foreign languages education? We can include many technologies on the list, but it is not always possible to have all of them in the class especially if they are expensive. So the technology worth using in the class and definitely an effect on the process of education is the internet [4].

How can we produce digital stories? Again we use the internet to find some information about the topic, pick some images and music. Then we have to use our creativity and special computer programs to edit our digital story. While working on the topic we learn a lot. And we can also improve our reading, writing, listen and speaking skills when we produce digital stories. Moreover, we can advance our artistic creativity and critical while getting the task completed [5].

But now students have great technologies to learn any language they want. Now students have a chance to bring the world to the class. There is no need to go anywhere. It is the time to tear down the walls of the class and see the world outside.

In the future, there will be students who can speak in different foreign languages fluently and there will be teachers that be proud and be happy to see their students succeed.

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